

We would be very grateful if you would answer all the questions but we understand if there are some that you prefer not to answer. There are no right or wrong answers.

Please ensure that you complete all sections before selecting 'Submit' at the end of the questionnaire. Once you have clicked 'Submit' you will not be able to return to the questionnaire or edit your answers.

If anything is unclear, please contact the Avian Contact Study Team by email avian-contact-study@bristol.ac.uk.

Consent ID:

Survey Progress

About you The following questions are about you

In which year were you born?

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

What is the first part of the postcode of your home address?

What is the first part of the postcode of your work address?

Does your main occupation involve contact with any type of bird(s)?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

What is your main occupation?

- Poultry farmer
- Dairy farmer
- Livestock farmer
- Arable farmer
- Farm labourer
- Veterinarian
- Veterinary assistant
- Veterinary nurse
- Animal health inspector or officer
- Meat hygiene inspector
- Butcher
- Slaughterer
- Conservationist
- Ecologist
- Environmental health professional
- Outdoor pursuits instructor
- Landscape gardener
- Groundsman or greenkeeper
- Falconer
- Gamekeeper
- Forestry worker
- Cutter or picker
- Other
- Survey tester

Please state your main occupation

How long have you been in this occupation?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 - 5 years
- 6 - 10 years
- 11 - 15 years
- 16 - 20 years
- More than 20 years
- Prefer not to say

What is your country of birth?

- England
- Northern Ireland
- Scotland
- Wales
- Not UK born
- Prefer not to say

If you were not UK born, please state the country in which you were born?

If you were not UK born, in which year did you move to the UK?

On a scale of 1-10, how would you rate your current health? (1 being very poor, 10 being excellent)

Has the seasonal (winter) flu vaccine provided by the NHS been recommended for you?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Have you been vaccinated against seasonal (winter) flu in the last 12 months?

- Yes as provided by the NHS
- Yes I paid for it myself
- No but I intend to get vaccinated
- No I am undecided
- No I am not intending to get vaccinated
- I do not know

When were you vaccinated?

Month (MM) _____

Year (YYYY) _____

I am not sure _____

What factors influenced your decision to get vaccinated? Please select all that apply.

- For protection against seasonal (winter) flu
- Convenience of appointment times
- Convenience of vaccine centre location
- The vaccine is safe - no side effects
- The vaccine is effective at reducing the risk of seasonal (winter) flu
- Other people I know are vaccinated
- The vaccine has been recommended for me
- For protection against avian influenza (bird flu)
- To protect other people

What factors have prevented you from getting vaccinated? Please select all that apply.

- I have not had time to get vaccinated
- I do not know where to get vaccinated
- It is too far/inconvenient to get vaccinated
- The vaccine is too expensive

What factors influenced your indecision or decision to not get vaccinated? Please select all that apply.

- The vaccine is too expensive
- I am not sure if the vaccine is effective
- The vaccine may cause short term side effects
- The vaccine may cause long term side effects
- I am not likely to catch seasonal (winter) flu
- I will not get very ill if I catch seasonal (winter) flu
- I am allergic to the vaccine
- It is better to get natural immunity
- Other

Please state what factors influenced your indecision or decision to not get vaccinated.

To the best of your knowledge, have you ever been exposed to avian influenza (bird flu)?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Have you ever been offered a test for avian influenza (bird flu)?

- Yes and I was tested
- Yes but I was not tested
- No
- I did not know there is a test

What was the result of this test?

- Positive I had avian influenza (bird flu)
- Negative I did not have avian influenza (bird flu)
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

If you were tested more than once for avian influenza (bird flu), what were the results of these tests?

- Tested positive at least once
- Always tested negative
- I do not know
- Prefer not to say

Have you ever been offered antiviral medication (oseltamivir®, also known as Tamiflu) for avian influenza (bird flu)?

- Yes and I accepted
- Yes but I declined
- No
- I cannot remember

Survey Progress 25% complete

Your contact with any type of domestic or wildlife birds The following questions are about your direct contact with any type of bird either domestic or wildlife

How frequently do you have direct contact* with any type of domestic or wild bird(s)?
*Direct contact means being within 2 metres of a bird.

- On a daily basis
- Several times a week
- A few times a month
- A few times a year
- Never

What type of bird(s) do you have direct contact* with? Please select all that apply.
*Direct contact means being within 2 metres of a bird.

Domestic Birds of prey Wild waterfowl Seabirds Pet birds

Other type of

domestic bird: _____

Other type of

birds of prey: _____

Other type of

wild waterfowl: _____

Other type of

seabird: _____

Other type of

pet bird: _____

Any other type of bird, please state: _____

How many birds of any type were you in direct contact* with on a typical day?

*Direct contact means being within 2 metres of a bird.

- 1 - 10
 11 - 100
 101 - 1 000
 1001 - 10 000
 10 001 - 100 000
 More than 100 000

If you are a bird owner, how many birds do you own?

- 1 - 10
 11 - 100
 101 - 1 000
 1001 - 10 000
 10 001 - 100 000
 More than 100 000
 I am not a bird owner

What type of contact have you had with any type of bird(s) on a typical day? Please select all that apply.

- Feeding
 Handling
 Touch waste/litter/eggs
 Culling
 Plucking
 Disposal
 Visual contact - you were within 2 metres of the birds but did not touch them
 Other

If other type of contact, please specify:

Why did you have contact with bird(s)? Please select all that apply.

- Occupational/related to work
 Non-occupational/not related to work

Do you use any biosecurity measures to limit the risk of catching avian influenza (bird flu)? Please select all that apply.

- I use face masks
 I use goggles
 I use gloves
 I change clothing when in contact with birds
 I use outer garments when in contact with birds
 I change boots
 I use boot covers
 I use a disinfecting footwear dip
 I wash/clean my hands after touching birds
 I wash/clean my hands before and after handling raw poultry meat
 I make sure raw poultry meat is fully cooked before eating
 I do not eat undercooked or raw poultry meat
 I make sure eggs are thoroughly cooked
 I do not eat raw eggs
 I do not remember
 None
 Other

If other, please specify:

Why do you use biosecurity measures? Please select all that apply.

- To prevent catching avian influenza (bird flu)
- For my protection against the birds
- For my protection against bird waste
- For my protection when handling feed
- For my protection against sawdust or straw
- To protect my birds
- Other

If other, please specify:

Because of the risk of avian influenza (bird flu), have you changed your practices when handling bird(s)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't think so

If you are a bird owner, are there any other livestock on your premises? Please select all that apply.

- Cattle
- Pigs
- Sheep
- Goats
- Oxen
- Donkeys
- Horses
- Other
- No other livestock on premises

If other type of livestock, please specify:

If you are a bird owner, do you have any domestic pets on your premises? Please select all that apply.

- Cats
- Dogs
- Guinea pigs
- Hamsters
- Rabbits
- Other
- No domestic pets on premises

If other type of domestic pet, please specify:

Survey Progress 50% complete

Your contact with other people The following questions are about your contact with other people, either relatives, friends, work colleagues and/or others

Please say how many people you have had direct contact with in the last 24 hours.

- 1 - 5
- 6 - 10
- 11 - 15
- 16 - 20
- More than 20

*Direct contact is either:

- Physical: when you met someone face-to-face and had physical contact either by a handshake, hug, kiss or contact sport

- Conversational: you met someone and exchanged at least a few words with the person

- By distance: you were within 2 metres of this person

Please say who the people were, their age group, where you had the direct contact, the type of contact, the length of time of contact and whether you were indoors or outdoors.

Contact 1

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 2

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 3

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 4

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 5

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 6

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 7

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 8

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 9

Who _____

Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 10

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 11

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 12

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 13

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 14

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 15

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 16

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 17

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 18

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 19

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

Contact 20

Who _____
Age group (years) _____
Where _____
Contact type _____
Contact time _____
Time spent... _____

What is the furthest distance you travelled from your home in the last 24 hours?

- 1 - 10 miles
- 11 - 20 miles
- 21 - 50 miles
- 51 - 75 miles
- 76 - 100 miles
- More than 100 miles

Survey Progress 75% complete

Your awareness of avian influenza (bird flu) The following questions are on what you know about avian influenza (bird flu)

How seen or heard information about the recent avian influenza (bird flu) outbreaks in the UK?

- I have seen or heard information
 I have not seen or heard any information
 I do not remember
-

Where did you find the information about avian influenza (bird flu)? Please select all that apply.

- Television
 Newspaper
 Social Media
 Online
 Family
 Friends
 Work Colleagues
 Veterinarians
 Defra (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs)
 APHA (Animal and Plant Health Agency)
 NFU (National Farmers Union)
 Other source
-

If other source, please specify:

How much risk do you think avian influenza (bird flu) currently poses to your physical health?

- Very high risk
 High risk
 Medium risk
 Low risk
 No risk at all
 I do not know
-

How much risk do you think avian influenza (bird flu) currently poses to the health of other people who work with birds?

- Very high risk
 High risk
 Medium risk
 Low risk
 No risk at all
 I do not know
-

How much risk do you think avian influenza (bird flu) currently poses to the health of your birds?

- Very high risk
 High risk
 Medium risk
 Low risk
 No risk at all
 I do not know
-

How much risk do you think avian influenza (bird flu) currently poses to your business/livelihood?

- Very high risk
 High risk
 Medium risk
 Low risk
 No risk at all
 I do not know
-

Were you aware of the control measures introduced for all poultry and captive birds in November and December 2022 to reduce the spread of avian influenza (bird flu)?

- Yes
 No, I was not aware
-

Which of the following control measures did you follow? Please select all that apply.

- Registered your birds with Defra/APHA
- Kept birds confined to housing with a solid roof
- Used wild bird deterrents such as scarecrows or spike strips or streamers
- Stored food water and bedding & equipment in an enclosed area
- Daily checked areas around bird housing to remove wild bird droppings or feathers
- Used clean clothing when entering bird housing areas
- Changed shoes when entering bird housing areas
- Used disinfectant foot dips when entering bird housing areas
- Reduced the number of people entering bird housing areas
- Reported sick or dead birds (wild or domestic) to Defra/APHA
- Did not handle sick or dead birds (wild or domestic)
- Kept pets away from sick or dead birds (wild or domestic)
- Housed new birds apart from existing birds for up to 4 weeks

Do you think enough is being done by public health services to control the spread of avian influenza (bird flu)?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Why do you think not enough is being done by public health services to control the spread of avian influenza (bird flu)?

Survey Progress COMPLETE!

Thank you!

Thank you very much for taking the time to complete this survey!

Please click on the 'Submit' button to save your data and end the survey.

If you would like to be informed of the survey results, please provide your email address

Alternatively, please check the Avian Contact Study website ([click here](#)) on which the results of this survey will be published.

If you have any questions or concerns about this survey or avian influenza (bird flu), please contact the Avian Contact Study Team by email avian-contact-study@bristol.ac.uk